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Impact of Infrastructure on FDI In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's infrastructure is the primary focus of this study, which examines FDI inflows from 1996 to 2018. The long-term relationship between Nigeria's infrastructure and FDI is now being studied. To keep up with the growing investment demand, economic researchers must understand what drives FDI. Infrastructure improves productivity, decreases costs, and enables trade. From 1996 to 2018, five infrastructure variables were used to examine the impact of a country's infrastructure on the level of foreign direct investment (FDI). The Eclectic Paradigm served as the theoretical foundation for this study, emphasizing the importance of infrastructure in luring foreign direct investment (FDI). Mobile cellular users and the quality of port infrastructure were found to promote FDI inflows. Nigeria's infrastructure lags behind its competitors due to its large population (200 million people), making it harder for international investors to invest as they had hoped. In order to ensure that Nigeria can attract more foreign direct investment, the resuscitation of these two subsectors is essential.

Keywords

Nigeria, FDI, Infrastructure

Introduction

Improvement in the quantity and quality of transport infrastructure can reduce the amount or cost of private inputs needed for a given output level. There is a growing recognition that Communication can act as a catalyst for development, enabling change across all sectors, helping countries unleash their economic potential in terms of productivity and competitiveness (especially in combination with other growth-promoting policies); offering the opportunity to leapfrog stages of both technology and development; and increasing overall economic efficiency by allowing the flow of relevant information. While several factors come into play in determining a country's attractiveness to FDI, there is growing literature on the role of Communication and its infrastructures as a determinant of such investment. Generally speaking, we know that FDI plays a crucial role in the growth of an economy. However, the development of foreign-invested enterprises also requires a stable and affordable power infrastructure. The influx of more and more foreign investment increases the pressure on electricity demand in the host country. This is a holistic economic model to determine whether a business should expand abroad through FDI. For our study, we will focus on the Location advantage which includes the availability of solid infrastructure. These advantages can be simply geographical (e.g. the Nigeria is the biggest economy and most populous nation in Africa and is moreover located next to the ocean) or are

present because of the existence of cheap raw materials, solid infrastructures, low wages, a skilled labor force or special taxes and tariffs and so on.

- In Africa, particularly sub-Saharan Africa, there is a generally low level of infrastructure development. From our introductory background, we have surmised that this scenario might be one of the reasons Africa's share of Direct Foreign Investment (FDI) is meagre.
- This study's primary objective is to empirically investigate the impacts of infrastructure on foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria from 1996 to 2018.
- Improvement in the quantity and quality of transport infrastructure can reduce the amount or cost of private inputs needed for a given output level.
- The reduction in supply costs is actual at the firm level and in the aggregate as total output per unit of input increases when government-provided infrastructure results in more efficient use of existing resources.
- There is a growing recognition that Communication can act as a catalyst for development, enabling change across all sectors, helping countries unleash their economic potential in terms of productivity and competitiveness (especially in combination with other growth-promoting policies); offering the opportunity to leapfrog stages of both technology and development; and increasing overall economic efficiency by allowing the flow of relevant information.
- While several factors come into play in determining a country's attractiveness to FDI, there is growing literature on the role of Communication and its infrastructures as a determinant of such investment.
- Generally speaking, we know that FDI plays a vital role in the growth of an economy.
- However, the development of foreign-invested enterprises also requires a stable and affordable power infrastructure. The influx of more and more foreign investment increases the pressure on electricity demand in the host country.

Literature review

This is a holistic economic model to determine whether a business should expand abroad through FDI. For our study, we will focus on the Location advantage, which includes the availability of solid infrastructure. These advantages can be simply geographical (e.g., Nigeria is the biggest economy and most populous nation in Africa and is moreover located next to the ocean) or are present because of the existence of cheap raw materials, solid infrastructures, low wages, a skilled labor force or special taxes and tariffs and so on. Infrastructure critical to an emerging economy like Nigeria includes roads, power, transportation, ports development, water and communication infrastructure. Ahmad et al. (2015) examined the impact of infrastructure on foreign direct investment in Malaysia from 1980 to 2013. Olagunjaye (2015) notes that the poor state of infrastructural facilities has been the malaise of Nigeria's economic development. The need for solid infrastructure in developing countries is more urgent than ever before. Poor infrastructural base is the primary cause of Nigeria's meager FDI inflow.

Assuncao and Onyema (2016) examined the factor influencing FDI inflow to Nigeria using primary data sourced from foreign firms in Nigeria. Similarly, Long et al. (2018) investigated the causal relationship between electricity consumption, foreign direct investment, and economic growth in Vietnam during the period 1990-2015. Nigeria needs to improve its investment climate to attract more foreign direct investment (FDI). Nigeria needs an improved infrastructure to boost economic activities and attract more investment. This study will examine the role of infrastructure in attracting Foreign Direct Investment inflow, which is expected to bring about economic growth in Nigeria.

It will also review the current state of the infrastructural development plans and policies in Nigeria and reforms that have been put in place to try to revitalize the country's infrastructure. In conclusion, this research will give suggestions and recommendations on how infrastructure can be improved in Nigeria to guarantee sustainable economic growth. High costs associated with inefficient transportation infrastructure in a labor-intensive country can hinder that economy from the benefits of attracting international firms to it. The diffusion of new Communications Infrastructure (e.g., Internet hosts, mobile phones) is a significant "pull" factor for FDI by recent studies. Higher economic growth requires more energy consumption; similarly, more efficient energy use needs a higher level of economic growth.

For example, Bekhet and Othman (2016) examined the causal relationship between electricity consumption and foreign direct investment in Malaysia. Salahuddin et al. (2018) examined the empirical effects of economic growth, electricity consumption, foreign direct investment (FDI), and financial development on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in Kuwait for the period of 1980-2013. Findings indicated that economic growth stimulates CO₂ emissions in both the short and long run. Abdouli and Hammami (2017) investigated the relationship between FDI inflows and economic growth in 17 MENA countries.

- This study will discuss the role of infrastructure in attracting Foreign Direct Investment inflow which ultimately is expected to bring about economic growth, and it will also review the current state of the infrastructural development plans and policies in Nigeria as well as reforms that have been put in place to try to revitalize the critical infrastructures in Nigeria.
- Ultimately as it concerns Nigeria, this research will try to fill the gap in the literature with regards to the role, impact and ways to improve the sector to ensure a functioning infrastructure sector that will guarantee sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.
- This section will analyze the relationship between each of our selected infrastructures (Transport, Power and Communication Infrastructure) and Foreign Direct Investment inflow.
- This nexus suggests that economic growth and energy consumption might be jointly determined because higher economic growth requires more energy consumption; similarly, more efficient energy use needs a higher level of economic growth.
- Nguyen and Nguyen (2013) and Anwar and Nguyen (2016), among others, have identified the two-way linkage between FDI and economic growth in which FDI promotes economic growth and, in turn, economic growth is viewed as a tool to attract FDI.

- The study confirmed the presence of co-integration between economic growth, renewable electricity consumption and foreign direct investment. Both renewable electricity consumption and foreign direct investment positively correlate with economic growth.
- 2018) examined the empirical effects of economic growth, electricity consumption, foreign direct investment (FDI), and financial development on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in Kuwait for the period of 1980-2013.
- Similar results were reported by Abdouli and Hammami (2017); they investigated the relationship between FDI inflows, energy consumption, and economic growth for a panel of 17 MENA countries throughout 1990-2012.

Analysis of Nigeria's Infrastructure

According to the United Nations traditional infrastructure index, Nigeria has one of the lowest levels of access to improved basic infrastructure anywhere in the world. Nigeria ranks 32 out of 54 countries in Africa, and among its global lower-middle-income peers, only Sudan and Papua New Guinea perform worse. By 2040 Nigeria is expected to rank only second-last in this group still. Given the considerable amount required, it is near impossible to expect the government to foot the entire bill. As a result, projects such as the Second Niger Bridge, the East-West Road, and the dredging of the River Niger are not attended to. As a result, projects such as the Second Niger Bridge, the East-West Road, dredging of the River Niger to allow sea-going vessels to dock at in-land ports, a standard gauge rail line connecting the state capitals and economic centers of Nigeria from North to South, power dams, electricity transmission lines, electricity distribution infrastructure and other critical infrastructure are not attended to, affecting the quality of economic growth, the creation of jobs and the enhancement of the economic well-being and standard of living of Nigerians.

So, how does Nigeria move forward? The Nigerian government clearly understands a substantial infrastructural gap that must be bridged. As such, the Nigerian public officials, as well as state governors and federal ministers, frequently visit advanced economies of the world such as the USA, Australia, Europe, China, Canada, Japan, and South Korea to implore foreign organizations, government, and individuals to invest in Nigeria promising to give them incentives like tax incentives, low-interest loan, grants, and increasing government expenditure on infrastructure, among others.

FDI inflows to the mining and quarrying sector increased from 22.9 percent to 43.7 percent in the same period. In 1995-99, foreign investments in all the sectors, except for mining and quarrying, fell significantly following the governance issues of the Abacha's administration, the former military Head of State, as well as the emergence of civil society, which was craving for the return of democracy in Nigeria. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria has skewed towards the mining and quarrying sector and the manufacturing sector. The agriculture sector, which used to be the mainstay of the Nigerian economy, received a minor inflow of FDI. Akinwale (2010) outlines the major infrastructure components to include the following: Power/Energy, Transport Infrastructure, and Communication infrastructure.

Despite this, Nigeria's power sector has been characterized by a high degree of operational inefficiency and underpricing. For this study, The World Bank looks at the transport infrastructure in Nigeria. Nigeria is one of the few African countries with direct flights to the United States. Nigeria's air transport and rail infrastructure are second only to South Africa in size, with a Herfindahl index¹ of 18 percent. The number of passengers carried in the Nigerian market increased from 400,000 to over 8 million annually in 2018. Air transport, passengers carried - Nigeria

Nigeria's port sector reform program was wide-ranging, detailed, and implemented on a scale unprecedented for this sector in Africa. The reforms were well planned, for the most part well implemented, and placed the country's port system on a much more sound footing. Nigeria has attracted over half the \$28 billion in private capital that develops new mobile networks across Africa. Nigeria has made significant progress in developing a national fiber-optic network by harnessing private sector investment. The government can limit public funds to areas where no other solution is possible, thereby saving significant fiscal resources. Nigeria's infrastructure challenges, though substantial, are not daunting given the strength of the national economy.

- In 2016, Nigeria had one of the lowest access levels to improved basic infrastructure anywhere globally, ranking 162 out of 186 countries, according to the United Nations traditional infrastructure index.
- To answer this question, The Nigerian government has put in place several infrastructural institutional frameworks over time to help in the development and sustenance of infrastructures in Nigeria.
- For this study, we will focus on three critical physical infrastructures that affect the inflow of Foreign Direct Investment: Power Infrastructure, Transport Infrastructure, and Communication infrastructure.
- Despite high levels of electrification, Nigeria's power sector has struggled to provide an adequate supply of reliable power.
- Nigeria's air transport market tripled in size between 2004 and 2007, mainly due to the rapid expansion of domestic services.
- In August 2010, Nigeria became one of the few countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (alongside Cape Verde, Ethiopia, and South Africa) whose safety oversight is considered good enough for the United States to allow direct flights by Nigerian carriers from Nigeria to the United States.
- Nigeria has also made significant progress in developing a national fiber-optic network by harnessing private sector investment.
- By liberalizing the market for fiber optic infrastructure, the country has seen substantial private sector investment in this area, leading to a solid backbone network interconnecting the significant cities.

Methodology

- Therefore our study will utilize econometric technique of the ordinary least squares (OLS) model to determine the effect of infrastructure towards attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria.

- One of the assumptions made about residuals/errors in OLS regression is that the errors have the same but unknown variance.
- This is known as constant variance or homoscedasticity.
- Durbin-Watson test for autocorrelation - Durbin-Watson's "d" tests the null hypothesis that the residuals are not linearly auto-correlated.
- The above tests are generally aimed at ascertaining that the regression model is the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) as described by the Gauss-Markov theorem.

Simon and Goes (2013) see ex post facto research is based on a fact or event that has already happened. Since this research focuses on the impact of infrastructure on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria, the critical infrastructure sectors of the economy Transport, Power and Communications Infrastructures will be analyzed within a regression model. The data-set will capture already computed and reported macroeconomic variables.

Description and Justification of Variables

Nigeria's infrastructure is vital for economic development, creating direct and indirect employment, supporting tourism and local businesses, and stimulating foreign investment and international trade. According to the World Bank, the higher the electricity consumption, the more productivity can be experienced in the economy. Nigeria's restructuring needs to have a certain level of Location advantage before a foreign company can decide to move its operations to another country, according to the Eclectic Paradigm of Ownership, Location and Internalization (OLI) Model. This research will use the econometric technique of the ordinary least squares (OLS) model to determine the effect of infrastructure towards attracting Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria. This shows whether each independent variable in the equation is consistent with the postulations of economic theory.

It expresses the mathematical relationship between the dependent and the independent or explanatory variables. For the selected model, Economic postulations suggest that an increase in the infrastructure levels will increase the inflow of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). The common signs of regression coefficients in the equation are $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5 > 0$. Table

- Independent Variable
- Dependent Variable

The Coefficient of determination (R^2) or the measure of goodness of fit is used to judge the explanatory power of the explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The higher the R^2 , the more the model can explain the changes in the independent variable. If R^2 equals one, it implies a 100% explanation of the variation in the dependent variable by the independent variable, which indicates a perfect fit of the regression line. The F-test dictates whether the linear regression model provides a good fit for the independent variables. Durbin-Watson's test for autocorrelation aims to ascertain that the regression model is the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) as described by the Gauss-Markov theorem. Homoscedastic in regression is a vital assumption; if the assumption is violated, you will not use regression analysis.

Interpretation & analysis of results

The government of Nigeria estimates that 84.60% of the total variation in FDI inflow is explained or caused by the independent variables in the model. Mobile Phone Subscribers - MPS (0.2812) and Seaport Infrastructure Quality - SIQ (0.2249) turned out positive and significant. An article by the Economic Times in 2018 seems to support the hypothesis that telecommunications infrastructure is essential to attracting foreign investment. According to our test result, Rail Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Rail lines (total route-km) in Nigeria, negatively affects FDI coming into the country. This is probably a reflection that the Nigerian aviation sector suffers from a poor reputation for operational efficiency and safety.

The advent of GSM Technology ushered in the arrival of Chinese Communication Giants Huawei and ZTE into the Nigerian economy. Rail Infrastructure (RIQ) and FDI - Nigeria has one of Africa's most extensive national rail networks. However, due to deficient performance and erratic service, traffic volumes have been in a long-term decline. According to our test result Rail Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria, has a positive relationship with FDI coming into the country. Even though Nigeria's port infrastructure still needs much improvement, due to the size of Nigeria in terms of market size and proximity to the Atlantic Ocean, the seaports in Nigeria serve as a hub for the whole West African region. The energy supply crisis in Nigeria is complex, stems from various issues, and has been ongoing for decades. Despite high levels of electrification, Nigeria's power sector has struggled to provide an adequate supply of reliable power. A 1% increase in Electric Power Consumption (Kwh per capita) will result in a 0.0049% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria. The research focused on the impact of Infrastructure component variables of FDI in Nigeria. This was ascertained using the multiple regression techniques with the E-Views Econometric Software.

It found that there is a negative relationship between FDI and Power Infrastructure. A 1% increase in the Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria will result in a 0.2249% increase in FDI coming into Nigeria.

- Using the E-Views 10 package, the parameter estimates that measure the effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable in both models were generated.
- According to our test result, Mobile Phone Subscribers, which serves as a proxy for the communication infrastructure in Nigeria, has a positive relationship with FDI coming into the country.
- Seaport Infrastructure (SIQ) and FDI - According to our test result, Rail Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria, has a positive relationship with FDI coming into the country.
- Our result shows that a 1% increase in the Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria will result in a 0.2249% increase in FDI coming into Nigeria.
- Our result shows that a 1% increase in Electric Power Consumption (Kwh per capita) will result in a 0.0049% decrease in FDI coming into Nigeria.
- However, despite high levels of electrification, Nigeria's power sector has struggled to provide an adequate supply of reliable power.

Conclusion

A close analysis of the results generally highlights that Nigeria. However, a big market rich in resources is still lagging behind its peers in terms of infrastructure, making it difficult for foreign investors to come into the country to invest expected. Power infrastructure is probably the most important because almost all economic activities require electricity to function, especially in the manufacturing sector. There is a need for the urgent revival of the rail infrastructure in Nigeria. The Nigerian government and the private sector should gear efforts towards resuscitating the ailing power sector, standardizing it, and devising other means of generating alternative power supply. The rail lines must also be connected to critical port facilities to enable easy and efficient movement of goods from the seaports into the various cities. Nigeria has been doing very well in mobile phone technology and the resulting subscriptions. Nigeria must have an efficient and reliable aviation sector. The rail lines must also be connected to critical port facilities to enable easy and efficient movement of goods from the seaports into the various cities. Nigeria's rural dwellers must be sensitized to the benefits of mobile phone usage in their daily personal and business activities. Nigeria has faced competition from nearby countries, Benin Republic, Togo, and Ghana, due to the cost of usage, port facilities, and processing time experienced in Nigerian ports. Nigeria must improve on these deficiencies, and they can even attract more port traffic. Nigeria has been guilty of poor maintenance culture, which has led to much of the existing infrastructure not being well maintained, renovated, or upgraded. Instead, the Nigerian government should ensure that the private sector has sufficient incentives to invest in infrastructure development. This is because the government cannot fund all infrastructure projects recently due to its limited capabilities. As such, the most efficient and cost-saving alternative is to open the doors to private investment.

Complete overview of this research

The development of foreign-invested enterprises also requires a stable and affordable power infrastructure. In Africa, particularly sub-Saharan Africa, there is a generally low level of infrastructure development. This may be one of the reasons why Africa's share of Direct Foreign Investment (FDI) is meagre. The development of foreign-invested enterprises also requires a stable and affordable power infrastructure. Poor infrastructural base is the primary cause of Nigeria's meagre economic development.

Infrastructure critical to an emerging economy like Nigeria includes roads, power, transportation, ports development, water and communication infrastructure. Nigeria needs an improved infrastructure to boost economic activities and attract more investment. The diffusion of new Communications Infrastructure (e.g., Internet hosts, mobile phones) is a significant "pull" factor for FDI. Higher economic growth requires more energy consumption; similarly, more efficient energy use needs a higher level of economic growth. Nigeria has one of the lowest levels of access to improved basic infrastructure anywhere in the world.

Given the considerable amount required, it is near impossible to expect the government to foot the entire bill. As a result, critical infrastructure such as the Second Niger Bridge, East-West Road, and dredging of the River Niger is not attended to. Nigeria's foreign direct investment (FDI) has skewed towards the mining and quarrying sector. Nigeria is one of the few African countries with direct flights to the United States. The

government can limit public funds to areas where no other solution is possible, saving significant fiscal resources.

According to the U.N traditional infrastructure index, Nigeria has one of the lowest access levels to improved basic infrastructure anywhere globally, ranking 162 out of 186 countries. Despite high levels of electrification, Nigeria's power sector has struggled to provide an adequate supply of reliable power. Nigeria's infrastructure is vital for economic development, creating direct and indirect employment, supporting tourism and local businesses, and stimulating foreign investment and international trade. This research will use the econometric technique of the ordinary least squares (OLS) model to determine the effect of infrastructure towards attracting FDI. The advent of GSM Technology ushered in the arrival of Chinese Communication Giants Huawei and ZTE into the Nigerian economy.

According to our test result Rail Infrastructure, which is proxied by the Quality of port infrastructure in Nigeria, has a positive relationship with FDI coming into the country. Nigeria is lagging behind its peers in terms of infrastructure, making it difficult for foreign investors to come into the country to invest expected. There is a need for the urgent revival of the rail infrastructure in Nigeria and an urgent upgrade of the power infrastructure. Nigeria's rural dwellers must be sensitized to the benefits of mobile phone usage in their daily personal and business activities. The rail lines must also be connected to critical port facilities to enable easy and efficient movement of goods from the seaports into the various cities.

References

- [1] Abdullah, A. (2013), Electricity power consumption, foreign direct investment and economic growth. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, 10(1), 55-65.
- [2] Acaravci, A., Ozturk, I. (2012), Electricity consumption and economic growth nexus: A multivariate analysis for Turkey. *The Amfiteatru Economic Journal*, 14(31), 246-257.
- [3] Ahmed, K., Bhattacharya, M., Shaikh, Z., Ramzan, M., Ozturk, I. (2017), Emission intensive growth and trade in the era of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) integration: An empirical investigation from ASEAN-8. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 154, 530-540.
- [4] Alam, M.S. (2006), Economic Growth with Energy. MRPA Working Paper. Available from <https://www.mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/1260>. [Last retrieved on 2006 Nov 20].
- [5] Alawiye, A.B., 2011. The power sector and industrial development in Nigeria case: Power holding company of Nigeria. Bachelor's Degree Thesis, International Business, Lahti University of Applied Sciences
- [6] Allcott, H., A. Collard-Wexler and S.D. O'Connell, 2014. How do electricity shortages affect productivity? Evidence from India. The 2014 NBER Winter IO/EEE Meetings, NBER Summer Institute Stanford.
- [7] Al-Mulali, U., Saboori, B., Ozturk, I. (2015), Investigating the environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis in Vietnam. *Energy Policy*, 76, 123-131.

- [8] Ang, J. (2009), Foreign direct investment and its impact on the Thai economy: The role of financial development. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 33(3), 316-323.
- [9] Anis, O., Nguyen, D.K., Rault, C. (2014), Causal interactions between CO2 emissions, FDI, and economic growth: Evidence from dynamic simultaneous-equation models. *Economic Modelling*, 42, 382-389.
- [10] Anyadike N. O. (2012). Poor Infrastructure: The Hindrance to Foreign Investment and Economic Development in Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business* Vol 4, No 4
- [11] Anyanwu, J. C. (2012). Why does foreign direct investment go where it goes? New evidence from African countries. *Annals of Economics and Finance*, 13(2), 425-462.
- [12] Arrow, K. (1962), The Economic implication of learning-by-doing. *Review of Economic Studies*, 29(1), 155-173.
- [13] Asiedu, E. (2006). Foreign direct investment in Africa: The role of natural resources, market size, government policy, institutions and political instability. *The World Economy*, 29(1), 63-77
- [14] Asiedu, E., & Lien, D. (2011). Democracy, foreign direct investment and natural resources. *Journal of International Economics*, 84(1), 99-111
- [15] Aslan, A., Apergis, N., Yildirim, S. (2014), Causality between energy consumption and GDP in the US: Evidence from wavelet analysis. *Frontier in Energy*, 8(1), 1-8.
- [16] Aytac, D., Guran, M.C. (2011), The relationship between electricity consumption, electricity price and economic growth in Turkey: 1984-2007. *Argumenta Oeconomica*, 2(27), 101-123.
- [17] Babatunde A. (2011). Trade Openness, Infrastructure, FDI and Growth in Sub-Saharan African Countries. *Journal of Management Policy and Practice* vol. 12(7)
- [18] Bang, V.T. (2008), Foreign direct investment and endogenous growth in Vietnam. *Applied Economics*, 40, 1165-1173.
- [19] Behname M. (2012). Foreign Direct Investment and Urban Infrastructure: An Evidence from Southern Asia. *Advances in Management & Applied Economics*, vol.2, no.4, 2012, 253-259
- [20] Bende-Nabende, A., Ferd, J.L. (1998), FDI, policy adjustments and endogenous growth multiplier effects form a small dynamic model for Taiwan, 1959-1995. *World Development*, 26, 115-130.
- [21] Bonfatti, R., & Poelhekke, S. (2017). From mine to coast: transport infrastructure and the direction of trade in developing countries. *Journal of Development Economics*, 127, 91-108
- [22] Canh, L.Q. (2011), Electricity consumption and economic growth in Vietnam: A cointegration and causality analysis. *Journal of Economics and Development*, 13(3), 24-36.
- [23] Chakrabarti R. et al (2012). Infrastructure and FDI: Evidence from district-level data in India.
- [24] Ciarreta, A., Zarraga, A. (2007), Electricity consumption and economic growth: Evidence from Spain. *Biltoki 2007.01*, Universidad del Pais Vasco. p1-20.

- [25] Davoud, M., Behrouz, S.A., Farshid, P., Somayeh, J. (2013), Oil products consumption, electricity consumption-economic growth nexus in the economy of Iran: Abounds test co-integration approach. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 353-367.
- [26] Dunning, J., Lundan, S. (2008), Institutions and the OLI paradigm of the multinational enterprise. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 25(4), 573-593.
- [27] Ericsson, J., Irandoust, M. (2001), On the causality between foreign direct investment and output: A comparative study. *The International Trade Journal*, 15, 122-132.
- [28] Escribano, A., Guasch, J. L., & Pena, J. (2010). Assessing the impact of infrastructure quality on firm productivity in Africa. *World Bank policy research working paper 5191*
- [29] Essia U. and Onyema J. (2012). Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria. *Journal of Money, Investment and Banking*, ISSN 1450-288X Issue 25 September, 2012
- [30] Ezzo, L.J. (2010), Threshold cointegration and causality relationship between energy use and growth in seven African countries. *Energy Economics*, 32(6), 1383-1391.
- [31] Estache, A. & Fay, M. (2010). Current Debates on Infrastructure Policy. In Spence, M. & Leipziger, D., *Globalization and Growth* (151-194). Washington, USA: The World Bank
- [32] Haddad, M., Harrison, A. (1993), Are there positive spillovers from direct foreign investment? Evidence from panel data for Morocco. *Journal of Development Economics*, 42, 51-74.
- [33] Hwang, J.H., Yoo, S.H. (2014), Energy consumption, CO2 emissions, and economic growth: Evidence from Indonesia. *Quality and Quantity*, 48(1), 63-73.
- [34] Ibrahiem, D.M. (2015), Renewable electricity consumption, foreign direct investment and economic growth in Egypt: An ARDL approach. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 30, 313-323.
- [35] Kao, C., Chiang, M.H. (2000), On the estimation and inference of a cointegrated regression in panel data. *Center for Policy Research*, 2000, 145.
- [36] Karikari, J.A. (1992), Causality between direct foreign investment and economic output in Ghana. *Journal of Economic Development*, 17(1), 7-17.
- [37] Karimi, M.S., Yusop, Z. (2009), FDI and Economic Growth in Malaysia. *MPRA Paper*, 14999(03).
- [38] Kasperowicz, R. (2014), Electricity consumption and economic growth: Evidence from Poland. *Journal of International Studies*, 7(1), 46-57.
- [39] Kraft, J., Kraft, A. (1978), On the relationship between energy and GNP. *Journal of Energy and Development*, 3(2), 401-403.
- [40] Kyophilavong, P., Shahbaz, M., Anwar, S., Masood, S. (2015), The energy-growth nexus in Thailand: Does trade openness boost up energy consumption? *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 46, 265-274.
- [41] Le Viet, A. (2009), FDI-Growth Nexus in Vietnam. Nagoya University. Mai. T.T. (2015), Mối quan hệ nhân quả giữa sản lượng điện tiêu thụ và tăng trưởng kinh tế ở các nước Asean. Master's Thesis in Economics. Ho Chi Minh City: University of Economics.

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